

THE CONCEPT AND PURPOSE OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES (USING THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS AS AN EXAMPLE)

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***Abstract.** Spiritual and educational work is a systematic educational activity aimed at improving the spiritual world, moral values, legal culture, and civic position of employees. The main goals are to cultivate spiritual maturity and literacy, strengthen the spiritual environment in society, develop in young people a sense of love for the Motherland and devotion to the people, ensure social and spiritual stability, and foster high spirituality and patriotism among employees, foster respect for national and universal values, prevent corruption, abuse, and violations of discipline, and improve the culture of working with the public.*

***Keywords:** spiritual and educational work, patriotic education, fostering self-sacrifice, legal awareness, legal knowledge, legal behavior, legal activism, moral education, national and religious tolerance.*

Introduction

It is widely acknowledged that spiritual and educational work is a systematic educational activity aimed at improving the spiritual world, moral values, legal culture, and civic position of employees. Spiritual and educational work is a set of activities aimed at enhancing the spiritual and educational potential of the population in society, fostering national pride, patriotism, humanism, spiritual purity, and respect for culture among citizens. The essence of this concept lies in fostering high moral values, spiritual perfection, and an understanding of civic duty and responsibility through spiritual education; promoting knowledge of science, culture, education, and historical heritage through educational work; enriching citizens' worldviews; widely disseminating spiritual and educational ideas among the population through the media, meetings, lectures, readings, and cultural events through propaganda and agitation; and preserving and developing national traditions, customs, and universal moral standards through the promotion of national and universal values.

The main goal is to foster spiritual maturity and education of the population, strengthen the spiritual environment in society, develop in young people a sense of love for the Motherland and devotion to the people, ensure social and spiritual stability, as well as promote the development of high spirituality and patriotism among employees, forming respect for national and universal values, preventing corruption, abuses and violations, improving the culture of working with the population. The goal of spiritual and educational work is to promote the spiritual growth of society, moral education, the formation of patriotism, humanism, the pursuit of knowledge, respect for national and universal values in citizens. In this regard, in order to enhance human spirituality, it is necessary to develop moral purity, universal human qualities and spiritual perfection; to educate the younger generation, it is necessary to develop such qualities as love for the Motherland, national pride, patriotism, honesty, devotion; To promote national and universal values, it is

necessary to foster respect for national traditions, customs, historical heritage, and cultural wealth. To strengthen the spiritual environment in society, it is necessary to ensure social stability based on morality and spirituality and combat negative vices. To enhance citizens' legal, educational, and cultural knowledge, it is necessary to develop a desire for knowledge, legal awareness, and culture. To increase social activism, it is necessary to encourage citizens to actively participate in society and help them understand their civic duty. It is important to emphasize that spiritual and educational work serves to create a spiritually healthy environment in society, raise a harmonious generation, preserve national identity, and ensure sustainable development.

The areas of spiritual and educational work in the Ministry of Internal Affairs system:

Fostering patriotism and self-sacrifice – involves cultivating respect for state symbols, national history, and the legacy of heroes and is an important area of spiritual and educational work aimed at developing in the younger generation a love for the Motherland, a willingness to defend it, putting the interests of the country and the people first, and a sense of selfless labor. What is patriotic education? Patriotism is a person's love for their homeland, a sense of responsibility for its peace, development, and protection, and a willingness to defend it under any circumstances. Education involves fostering love for the homeland, respect for national pride and historical heritage, an understanding of peace and stability, strengthening national defense capabilities, and raising legal, political, and spiritual values.

What is cultivating self-sacrifice? Self-sacrifice is selfless work for the good of the country, people, and society, and a willingness to sacrifice one's life if necessary. The main goal of education is to put the interests of society and the people above personal interests, to instill in children hard work, patience, courage, and responsibility, to teach them to understand their duty to family, society, and the homeland, and to set an example of heroism, courage, and bravery. It can be clearly observed that the goals of patriotic and selfless education include ensuring education based on national values, strengthening outreach efforts in educational institutions, families, and public organizations, informing about historical heroes and modern-day selfless individuals, encouraging service to the Motherland through increased social engagement, fostering respect for the army, and preparing for military service. To further enhance this process, it is necessary to read patriotic literature, meet with teachers, military personnel, and selfless individuals, conduct spiritual and educational events, organize holidays, visit museums and historical sites, and intensify community service.

The findings indicate that improving legal culture is a combination of educational, practical, and pedagogical work aimed at developing citizens' conscious attitudes toward laws, rights, and responsibilities, and increasing their level of legal knowledge and engagement. The main goal of enhancing legal culture is to increase citizens' legal awareness, foster respect for the law, ensure that everyone understands their rights and responsibilities, strengthen the rule of law and public order in society, protect young people from crime, and engage them in the fight against crime.

The key concepts of legal culture include legal awareness, legal knowledge, legal behavior, and legal activity.

The legal awareness is a person's legal knowledge and a conscious attitude toward it.

The legal knowledge is knowledge of the Constitution, laws, civil and criminal law, and all codes.

The legal behavior is a person's actions in accordance with legal norms.

The legal activity is an individual's active participation in exercising their rights and maintaining law and order in society.

It is evident from the data that enhancing legal culture include educational activities, propaganda through the media, legal education in educational institutions, legal consultations and assistance, and the provision of laws and legal literature. Educational activities are widely implemented through legal classes, seminars and trainings, legal weeks, open classes, and meetings with specialists (lawyers and legal professionals). Media outreach is widely implemented through legal programs on television, radio, the internet, and legal information on social media. In educational institutions, legal education is widely implemented through fundamentals of law classes in schools and universities, and legal issues are covered in the curriculum. It should be noted that legal assistance is widely disseminated through free legal consultations to the public, organizing "legal information days," distributing laws and legal literature, distributing collections of laws, manuals, and brochures, and creating access to information resources and legal portals. This work achieves the following results:

- citizens know and obey the laws;
- crime rates are reduced;
- each person understands their role and duty in society;
- the foundation for building a democratic and rule-of-law state is laid.

Moral education involves strengthening work ethics, discipline, and honesty and is an educational process aimed at developing high moral qualities in individuals: humanity, honesty, patriotism, kindness, truthfulness, responsibility, justice, and other positive qualities. The main goal of moral education is to develop moral consciousness and moral behavior, instill honesty, good intentions, conscientiousness, and patriotism, develop worthy relationships in the family, school, and society, and instill in young people a sense of duty and responsibility in society, respect for others, and self-control. The main areas of moral education include humanistic education, civic education, patriotic education, collective moral education, and aesthetic moral education. The content of moral education is to develop in children a sense of kindness, compassion, and tolerance for others; an awareness of rights and responsibilities in society; a sense of love and devotion to the Motherland; and the cultivation of mutual respect, etiquette, and a desire for beauty and proper behavior and speech.

The means of moral education:

Personal example – setting a good example through the behavior of parents, teachers, and members of society;

Fiction – explaining moral content through books, poems, and stories;

Conversations and debates – exchanging opinions on various topics and formulating conclusions;

Cultural events – strengthening morality through visits to the theater, museums, and national holidays.

Moral education is a special educational and upbringing activity in educational institutions.

Effective moral education fosters a healthy atmosphere in society, where people live in an atmosphere of mutual respect and kindness, young people grow up to be upstanding, conscientious, and responsible individuals, and honesty and fairness are paramount in social relations.

Domestic and psychological support is a system of material, domestic, and psychological assistance aimed at improving the internal stability and family environment of employees and assisting them in overcoming various life challenges. It is generally accepted that domestic support

is a type of assistance aimed at meeting a person's daily needs, including food, clothing, housing, transportation, education, and medical care. The main forms of assistance include food assistance, housing, assistance with clothing and household items, assistance with transportation and medical care, and support for low-income individuals and those with disabilities. Psychological support is a combination of consultations and assistance that helps individuals overcome mental disorders, stress, fear, anxiety, and depression.

The main forms of assistance include psychological counseling (individual or group), stress and mental tension management sessions, motivational interviews and training, psychotherapy sessions (if necessary), and special programs for youth, women, children, and other special groups. This type of support aims to facilitate people's adaptation to social life, the spiritual and material recovery of those in difficult life situations, support for students, youth, the elderly, and vulnerable groups, ensure social stability and peace of mind in groups in need of protection, and improve the overall quality of life. It has been shown through analysis that its scope of application includes psychological services in schools and universities, material and household assistance in the community and in social service institutions, programs for women, children, and the elderly in difficult life situations, and psychological support for employees of large organizations and enterprises. It is imperative to recognize that individuals develop mental resilience, self-confidence, and peace of mind; citizens in difficult life situations return to life and become active citizens; social equality and stability are achieved.

It is necessary to highlight the fact that national and religious tolerance is a respectful attitude toward representatives of different nationalities and religions, based on respect, mutual understanding, and peaceful coexistence among representatives of different nationalities, religions, customs, and beliefs. It is an important value that ensures stability and unity in society. National tolerance is a benevolent, respectful, and equal attitude toward representatives of different nationalities and peoples. This means recognizing the right of every person to live freely and develop their national customs, language, and culture. Its core values are the maintenance of interethnic peace, respect for national culture and traditions, friendly relations with representatives of other nationalities, and mutual understanding and cooperation in a multiethnic society.

Religious tolerance is a respectful, patient, and tolerant attitude toward people of different religions and beliefs, recognizing their right to freedom of religion. Its essence lies in ensuring interfaith harmony, respect for all religions and beliefs, the right to freely practice one's religion without violence and coercion, and respect for religious literature and symbols. The goals of fostering tolerance are to ensure interethnic and interfaith harmony in society, to develop a broad worldview and respect for others in young people, to foster immunity to violence and intolerance, to build a mutually tolerant and harmonious society, and to ensure the practical realization of human rights and freedoms.

Methods of fostering tolerance:

Educational activities – conducting tolerance lessons and events in schools and universities;

Cultural events – organizing multinational festivals and traditional culture days;

Social projects – conducting trainings and meetings promoting interethnic and interreligious friendship;

Media – preparing programs, articles, and videos promoting tolerance;

Family education – raising a child in a spirit of respect and understanding for others.

As a result, peace and stability will be established between peoples and religions, violence and religious extremism will have no place in society, every person will live freely, with their own beliefs and culture, human rights will be ensured, and solidarity among citizens will grow.

Conclusion

The forms and methods of spiritual and educational work include lectures and seminars on legislation, spiritual heritage, and morality; spiritual hours (weekly educational meetings); social projects (events involving youth, schools, courtyards, reading and spiritual clubs) to create an educational environment for employees; and psychological training (skills for appropriate behavior in stressful, conflict-ridden, and stressful situations). It is fundamentally important to acknowledge that a spiritual person is a perfect person.

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